

Framework for developing a mobility management program for ageing adults

Report Round 4 – The MOBiLe Consensus Study

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1. CONTEXT

By 2030, Europe's proportion of population aged 80 years or more will have increased by 47.9% compared to 2010 moving from a total of 23.1 million to a total of 35.6 million [1]. These predicted demographic changes require solutions to help ageing population stay autonomous as long as possible. Combined cognitive and functional impairment are the leading reasons for permanent admission to nursing-homes [2]. A recent longitudinal study showed life-space mobility to be a predictor of admission to nursing-homes independent of initial level of activity of daily living, cognitive status, or presence of depression [3]. This suggests the issues are more than their health condition, it is the loss of accessibility to places of importance that contributes to loss of independence.

Mobility is usually defined by an individual's capacity to move around. Mobility also can be perceived as an emotional experience, means of participation in the natural environment, a social need [4], a source of stimulation, or an expression of personal autonomy [5].

The role of mobility in making occupations possible is therefore determinant in linking their actual mobility to their quality of life. The place mobility holds therefore highly depends of the importance people attribute to their out-of-home occupations [6]. Some of these occupations substantially contribute to the overall social capital; for example social care, childcare, and volunteering [7]. Loss of mobility can also cause social isolation [8]. The loss of physical activity contributes to loss of activity, this in turn reduces cognitive functions and physical condition [9]. Sedentary lifestyles increase the risk of developing slow gait and cognitive complaints by 1.76 times and usually precedes the appearance of mild cognitive impairment [10]. Maintaining an active lifestyle and getting to places of importance seems primordial seems fundamental in conserving quality of life [11].

The effects of forced driving cessation on mental health is an example of consequences of unwanted reduced mobility [12]. In our society, the car is indeed recognised as a major factor in the inequalities in travel that influence health [13]. Driving cessation without alternative means of mobility is known to lead to social isolation and depression [14, 15, 16]. People from rural areas been more vulnerable than those from urban areas. It is of a public health interest [17] to explore new means of assistance to make this transition acceptable [18]. Improving infrastructures is one way to tackle the problem; another is to address the problem of mobility in all its complexity by planning person-centred personalised interventions. This is because mobility is not only related to the environment but also to cognitive, psychosocial, physical, and financial aspects of each individual's life [19].

Lifestyle interventions seem to be best placed to find adapted personalised solutions [20]. In many countries, older patients are referred to occupational therapists to assess their fitness to drive and find adapted solutions to their mobility issues [21]. These programs are however focused on providing a clear assessment of fitness to drive or to help people cease driving. Little is done to help people find solutions during transport transition. There is a need for a mobility driving management program to help people find adapted mobility solutions responding to individual needs. However little is known about what is expected from such programs and how they need to be structured [22].

2. STUDY OBJECTIVE

The aim of this Delphi study is to find a consensus for defining program goals, conceptual framework, domains of change, program construct - including endpoints and therapeutic objectives - for the framework of a Mobility Management Program designed to help older drivers cease driving.

3. DISCUSSED FRAMEWORK

3.1. Aims of the program

The consensus group agreed the program should mainly seek to facilitate the transition to alternative transport and guide clients through their adjustments in becoming non-drivers. The main goal is to have people become autonomous in managing future changes in transport needs within their own network. The expected impact of a program is to ensure mental and physical well-being, maintain meaningful occupations, favour social engagements within the community, and assure road safety.

3.2. Conceptual framework

3.2.1 Underlying theoretical models

Consensus group members identified and validated underlying theoretical framework to define the stages of the process, to structure expected domains of change, and to consider approaches to achieve endpoints. The main difficulty the consensus group had to face was finding appropriate strategies to have clients own their decision for change when such changes are known to be challenging for older people (Continuity Theory of Normal Ageing) [23]. Whatever the underlying theory, it seems primordial they lead to adapted personal solutions that can maintain an occupational balance with minimal changes.

To define the stages of the process, we opted for the Transtheoretical Model of Behaviour Change [24] that was also used in the Driving Cessation Process Model [25]. To include broader aspects of interventional programs, we also relied on the Health Action Process Approach [26], closely related to the Self-efficacy Theory [27].

For structuring domains of change, when possible, we used the Behavioural Change Technique taxonomy developed by Michie, Abraham, Cane and Wood [28]. This approach cannot however be used for changes that concern infrastructures or supportive networks including caregivers.

For defining the approach, we relied on the Transactional Model [29] and the Client-Centeredness Goal Setting Approach [30]. Suggested components of the program relied on many underlying theories including Theory of Reasoned Action, Social Learning Theory, Social Cognitive Theory, Cognitive Adaptation Theory, Goal Theory, Self-regulation Theory, Intrinsic Motivation Theories, and Self-determination Theory.

3.2.2 Settings

Members of the consensus group had to accommodate important differences between countries and regions. The final framework was designed to fit all these settings. The provided framework therefore voluntarily does not provide indication on how clients are informed of the program and who delivers the program. This leaves freedom for adapting the framework to regional situations. The main factor all members of the consensus seem to agree on was that the program is designed for countries that have a health system that is more oriented towards person-centred care.

3.2.3 Target population

Given the importance accorded in anticipating future difficulties, the consensus group decided the program should be addressed to all people who have difficulties in considering alternatives ways of maintaining their occupations if they were to cease driving. Ideally, the program should therefore mainly concern people with emerging difficulties before driving cessation becomes urgent. However, the framework was designed to also suit those that are already deemed unfit to drive. It was decided that, when possible, the program should target the client's caregiver. Caregivers are therefore to be integrated in the process of change as soon as possible and the program also sets their occupational balance as a priority.

3.2.4 Implementation

To implement the program, close collaboration with local authorities, health care providers, driving centres, and a representative group for older people seems essential. Those commissioning the service have to make resources available to run the program at a reasonable cost for participants. The most important aspects of the program that needs to be defined for each setting are:

- ways to recruit and train those that will deliver the programs,
- means to inform target population of the existence of the program,
- means for clients to identify programs and to register on those they want to follow (i.e. diversity in location and schedules),
- means to identify patients' existing networks that could be involved in the program,
- ways to make the support material available for the components of the program.

3.3. Domains of change

Reported expected changes did not only concern behavioural changes for those entering the program but also important modifications in other domains such as supportive networks, infrastructures and behaviour for people that are not in the program (friends, relatives, volunteers, etc.)

The consensus group identified eight possible domains of changes that are described in the first column of **Table 1** and concern: transport, location, social interactions, activities, self-efficacy, support network, physical and cognitive functions, and infrastructures.

3.4. Program construct and description designed from the emerging consensus

The program framework was developed from two main constructs: the time-frame set by the transtheoretical model and the objectives set by the defined domains of change. The first made it possible to agree on stages clients go through and expectations for changes within each of them. The second had us integrate expected changes (i.e. domain of changes) within the set time-frame. This was done respecting a person-centred approach that also focused on managing caregivers. The consensus group therefore defined endpoints and therapeutic objectives that were set in different temporal stages.

3.4.1 Stages of progression

Figure 1 summarizes the group's consensus for defining the program's framework. This figure can be read from left to right. Human resources are described for each step using abbreviations put between brackets. The left part of the figure describes how clients and their caregiver enter the program, the central part describes stages of the program, the right part of the figure describes expected long term outcomes and impact of the program. For each step, assumptions are marked using a red triangle. Client, caregiver, relatives, friends, volunteers, supportive groups, social workers, and healthcare professionals will constitute a supportive network that will potentially be concerned by changes. Caregivers play a key-role within this network. The objective of the entire program is to help clients and caregivers become self-efficient in managing this network and find adapted solutions to maintain their mobility and manage emerging changes.

Within the framework, three distinctive phases can be described: the anticipating phase, the changing phase, and the functioning phase. These overlap the stages described within the transtheoretical model for which we will give a more detailed description.

Timing

The consensus group insisted the timing of the distinct steps within the program needed to be adaptable to individual differences in duration of transition. The entire program was initially planned to last six months. However, to adapt the program to individual situations, it should be possible to either shorten or lengthen each planned stage. The program should also make it possible to override expected endpoints of one stage and move on to the next. This is to account for clients who might have difficulties in being consistent with their decisions and often shift opinions. It is also for those who would clearly benefit from what lays ahead to experience the expected changes. Stages can therefore be seen as modules that are linked one after another but that can be run in parallel when useful.

Stage 1 - "Consideration"

In this stage, clients are confronted by age related changes and the difficulties this might lead to. It therefore also concerns clients who are not required to cease driving but would like to anticipate the problem. Caregivers are integrated at this stage of the program to form a duo client/caregiver. The caregiver's contribution in the decision process is largely dependent of the client's severity of cognitive impairment. Ideally, clients enter the program early enough to have a comfortable time-frame during which changes can be brought progressively before driving cessation occurs. During this stage, clients are led to focus on their strengths instead of their difficulties. They are engaged to discuss potential future scenarios of failing health and impact on driving abilities. They can also be challenged about the difficulties they experience in whilst driving. With a better understanding of the problem, the decision to cease driving shifts from an imposed external decision to a personal decision motivated by their sense of self-responsibility. Clients are asked to consider their positive experiences, such as the advantages in driving cessation and witnesses from peers. Clients are made aware of the importance of communication skills to manage mobility with caregivers and community and health support. The stage is considered complete (endpoint 1) when they understand and manage normal grieving process, and change their emotional attachment to driving from a right to a privilege. They are also led to consider the advantage of being able to successfully use alternative mode of transport, to realize it will enable them to engage out-of-home activities and to believe in their capabilities. Thereby making the idea of change possible.

Stage 2 - "Acceptance"

In this stage, clients make the decision of transition their own. Clients accept their need for change. They can create their own narrative for their personal reasons for discontinuing driving and be emotionally and rationally convinced that such a change is necessary. They can try out alternative means of transport to experience their advantages. This stage ends once clients own the decision of transition and can create their own narrative of change in cultural adaptation. Clients who suffer from anosognosia and are unable to accept the situation (i.e. not to confuse with the denial phase of grief), are to move on to the next stage and negotiate solutions with their caregiver. In the absence of a caregiver, this role should be taken by a person of the client's choice.

Stage 3 - "Action"

In this stage, clients explore possible alternatives to chose those that are most adapted in maintaining meaningful activities. Clients develop planning skills and learn to set goals. They discuss transport options with family, caregivers or community support. Clients adjust performance patterns of valued activities to meet the availability of alternative transportation. They are provided with support in developing a feasible plan for how they will implement these changes, and in problem-solving unforeseen circumstances. They improve their capacity for change and movement in transport. This involves trying out different ways and means of transport in a try and error approach. This stage ends once clients have negotiated a personal plan for alternative mobility options.

Stage 4 - "Autonomy"

In this phase, clients/caregivers and their support network take confidence in their ability to implement and adapt chosen changes in behaviour. This longer phase consists of a follow-up period during which solutions are adjusted and client/caregiver learn to perceive instability as an ongoing challenge. Indeed, perpetual rehabilitation is necessary depending on the changes (health decline of the client/caregiver, transport modification, house moving, etc.). There is a progressive decrease in the support provided by the program as clients/caregivers and their support network recover their autonomy by working together in choosing appropriate strategies. This stage ends once the client/caregiver and support network's autonomy is functional to manage emerging changes in mobility.

3.4.2 Links to domains of change

Changes are initiated by clients to achieve an occupational balance. These changes not only apply to self-behaviour, but also concern other individuals including those that constitute the functional network for mobility around the client. **Figure 2** illustrates these categories of domain of changes in blue. This figure shows how these link to specific stages of the program during which changes are expected to occur.

4. FUTURE DEVELOPMENT

The consensus group agreed that two important aspects of the program should be left to other methods to find optimal solutions for the program. First, the modality and components of the program itself need to be defined. This requires a systematic review to identify the optimal methods to enhance wanted changes. Second, the resources to implement the program could not be described. These are dependant of local situations (available infrastructures, legal requirements, health care professionals that could deliver the program, etc.) and ought to be defined in close collaboration with authorities in each country.

This study has provided a framework from which it is now possible to construct innovative programs that can fit regional constraints.

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6. TABLES AND FIGURES

Domains	Subdomains	Examples
Transport	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Use public transports ▪ Use transportation assistance ▪ Use individualized mean of locomotion 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Help learn to read a bus timetable. ▪ Organise daughter to drive for visit to ophthalmologist. ▪ Learn to use a gopher (a four wheeled scooter).
Location	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modify destination for occupation ▪ Relocate occupation at home ▪ Modify place of residency 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Change hairdresser. ▪ Redesign living room to welcome card players at home. ▪ Move to secondary residency closer to relatives.
Social interaction	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accept help from others ▪ Use of technologies for communication ▪ Change context of interactions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Accept been driven by neighbour. ▪ Use social media to communicate with grandchildren. ▪ Organise art workshops at home instead of attending classes in town.
Activity	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Modify occupational priorities ▪ Modify occupational roles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Relinquish voluntary work at library. ▪ Have grandchildren sleep at home instead of babysitting at theirs. ▪ Have relative plan online shopping.
Self-efficacy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve self-awareness ▪ Improve self-confidence ▪ Improve self-management 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Help endorse the feeling of need of change. ▪ Overcome feelings of unsafety by considering having a relative over the phone whilst waiting for the bus. ▪ Become able to reorganise activities during absence of caregiver for a week.
Support network	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Maintain caregiver's occupational balance ▪ Coordinate community services ▪ Facilitate medical / social services 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Providing support to caregiver to help manage mobility and prevent overload. ▪ Call the volunteers transport to get to the supermarket. ▪ Coordinate community health services
Physical / Cognitive functions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Improve balance and confidence in walking. ▪ Use an auxiliary mean to facilitate walking. ▪ Improve cognitive processing speed through exercises.
Infrastructure		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ In case of snow, ask community worker to salt sidewalk to make access to train station easier and safer. ▪ Have a bench installed at the bus-stop.

Table 1: Structure of domains of change and examples of possible changes

Figure 1: Framework for the development of Mobility Management Programs

